

NEPHRON STRUCTURES IN RATS TREATED WITH PACLITAXEL FOR BREAST CANCER

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Annotation. Paclitaxel chemotherapy drugs are mitosis inhibitors, block cell division, disrupt the function of microtubules and some enzyme proteins, and also change the metabolism of amino acids and some other substances, such as nucleic acids, lipid synthesis, and affect cellular respiration.

Key words: cancer, carcinogen, PAU, chemotherapy, sarcomas, application.

Relevance. Paclitaxel, a drug used in cancer chemotherapy, is a mitosis inhibitor, and this group of chemotherapy drugs is of plant origin[3]. They block cell division, disrupt the function of microtubules and some enzyme proteins. They change the metabolism of amino acids and some other substances, such as nucleic acids, fat synthesis, and affect cellular respiration [2,5]. This drug has been widely used for chemotherapy since the 90s of the last century. Paclitaxel was first isolated from the Pacific yew (*Taxus baccata*) in the 1960s. Today, mitosis inhibitors are widely used to treat breast cancer [1,4].

The subject of the study was 52 white outbred female rats aged 6 months under normal vivarium conditions.

Material and methods. The experiments were carried out in a vivarium on 52 white outbred female rats. It involved 6-month-old rats. The experiments complied with the ethical rules for the use of animals and the requirements of the Helsinki Congress. Before the start of the experiments, all mature rats were quarantined for one week, and after eliminating somatic or infectious diseases, they were transferred to the vivarium mode under the same conditions as usual. During the experiment, the behavior and physiological state of animals in the standard and experimental groups were monitored. The rats were divided into 2 groups (n = 52): control group 1 (n = 40); Cancer rats of group 2 (n = 12) were administered intravenous paclitaxel at a dose of 0.2 mg/kg and 0.7 ml of distilled water intragastrically through a metal gastric tube for 21 days.

Research results. We observed various pathological changes in 6-month-old rats when they were treated with paclitaxel-based chemotherapy in a breast cancer model. Visual assessment did not reveal differences between the kidneys of the 6-month group of rats with breast cancer after chemotherapy with

paclitaxel and the rats of the 1st experimental group, but the organometric parameters of the kidneys remained significantly lower than the values of the control group at any time.

Thus, when exposed to the body of rats with breast cancer, a decrease in both the linear size of the kidneys and the quantitative size was observed, in comparison with animals in the control group of the experiment. It was found that the decrease in the relative mass of the kidneys persists.

A histomorphometric study of the renal corpuscles of intracortical nephrons showed that in 6-month-old rats with breast cancer in the experimental group after chemotherapy, the total area of the renal corpuscles ranged from 2684.97 μm^2 to 2768.67 μm^2 , with an average of 2738.27 \pm 46.65 μm^2 experimental group. Compared with group 1, it is 7.02% less than group 1, the area of the choroid glomerulus ranges from 2400.76 μm^2 to 2454.34 μm^2 , on average 2427.08 \pm 34.53 μm^2 , which is 5.68% less than the 1st group, and the lumen area of the capsule ranges from 402.81 mm^2 to 422.83 mm^2 , on average 413.26 \pm 32.09 mm^2 , which is 12.73% less than the 1st experimental group.

Conclusions. A microscopic examination of the kidneys of rats from the 2nd group at 6 months of age revealed signs of pathological engorgement of the capillaries of the vascular glomerulus. At the same time, the sizes of the renal corpuscles of this group were reduced compared to the 1st group of experimental animals due to a decrease in the lumen of the capsule and the vascular glomerulus, which indicates a decrease in its filtration processes.

Chemotherapy with paclitaxel caused the most pronounced changes in the structure of the kidneys. A microscopic examination of rat kidneys after chemotherapy revealed a number of features in the structure of nephrons. At the same time, the renal corpuscles of the nephrons have retained their structure, but among the preserved renal corpuscles, damaged renal corpuscles are often detected. In some kidney cells, damaged vascular glomeruli are found, which indicates the presence of red blood cells in the filtrate, that is, in the space of the nephron capsule. Cortical nephrons in the kidneys of 6-month-old rats with mammary cancer treated with chemotherapy in the experimental group showed that most of the renal corpuscles were smaller due to a decrease in the capsule lumen compared with the control group of experimental animals.

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